

Thinking outside the box.

Was Roentgen's discovery serendipitous or purposeful?

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And indeed, it may safely be said that unexpected inspirations are
produced by no other means than by the expectation of
them. (Robert Musil, *The man without qualities*,
First Book, section 28)

Abstract:

Roentgen's discovery of x-rays is often referred to as a classic example of serendipity. This paper calls for a revision of this position. We argue that the choice of setup for the experiment of November 8, 1895, the day of the discovery of X-rays, was not accidental, but purposeful. We believe that Roentgen was able to deduce some irregularities from publications by Lenard and Hertz. He was looking for and found invisible radiation, albeit in a form that had not been discovered before.

Serendipity is finding something of value while seeking something entirely different. The term has a long history in the antiquarian world but has been in vogue in science since the 1930s. The discovery of x-rays in 1895 by the physicist Wilhelm Conrad Roentgen (1845-1923) is often seen as a textbook example of serendipity. [1-3] But is this right? What was Roentgen looking for? All his lab notes were burned by will after his death. So, to find out what he was looking for, let's focus on the events leading up to the discovery. Roentgen was appointed professor of physics at the University of Würzburg in 1888. Before his discovery he already had a reputation as experimenter. [4, 5] The concerns of the rectorship (1893-1894) halted his research for a while. Thereafter Roentgen again focused on experimental research. He turned his attention to the cathode ray tube.

Cathode ray tube

Cathode rays were in the spotlight at the time, especially among his fellow countrymen, the physicists Helmholtz (1821-1894), Goldstein (1850-1930), Hertz (1857-1894) and Lenard (1862-1947). He was well aware of their publications, but he did not have time to do his own research on the cathode ray tube until the end of October 1895, as he says himself in one of the few existing interviews. [6] He was particularly inspired by Lenard's great 1894 article on the properties of cathode rays at atmospheric pressure and in evacuated tubes. [7] So he asked Lenard for advice on the ion tube he was using. [4, 8] But to discover the X-rays, he did not need Lenard's tube. And while Lenard covered his tube with metal, Roentgen used cardboard. Why did he do that? Why didn't he use metal or black fabric like his assistant and friend Zehnder (1854-1949)? [9] What was the rationale?

Investigation of contradictions

In his article Lenard writes that cardboard is not transparent to cathode rays, but he also notes that a photographic plate covered with cardboard, 0,3 mm thick, turns black. These

statements contradict each other. This observation may have been exactly the reason for Roentgen to wrap his tube in cardboard. With that cardboard he could not only cover the disturbing fluorescence of the glass of the tube, but he could also make observations behind the cardboard to see if the same unexpected effects occurred as in Lenard's experiments. Roentgen may also have noted Lenard's statements that an electroscope loses electrical charge at a distance of 30 cm at atmospheric pressure, although Lenard had previously observed that cathode rays in the atmosphere only have a range of 8 cm. [7] These two contradictory observations in Lenard's article may have raised Roentgen's expectations about the outcome of his experimentation. Presumably he was not unprepared when he saw a barium cyanuric screen light up, even at a distance of 2 meters.

And there was more. Roentgen was probably struck by an additional observation made in Lenard's article, as well as in an 1892 article by Hertz. Hertz describes an enhancing illumination of fluorescent glass (uranium glass) behind a metal plate, which is bombarded with cathode rays. [10] Lenard also reports on this phenomenon. Both researchers think this amplification is caused by reflection of the light from the fluorescent material on the metal (aluminum).

But Roentgen realized that the aluminum gave a better production of a new kind of rays. He wrote this in a letter dated January 28, 1896 to the physicist Emil Warburg, professor of physics in Berlin. [11] The letter was in response to a request from Warburg for information on Roentgen's curriculum for his nomination as corresponding member of the Academy. In the same letter, Roentgen thanks Warburg for his great help in preparing the demonstration of his discovery to Kaiser Wilhelm II on 12 January 1896, at the palace in Berlin. Apparently at this meeting, he had recommended Warburg which tubes to use. He returns to this in more detail in his letter.

He wrote:

Die Ihnen empfohlenen Röhren haben sich sehr gut bewährt, wenn man die der Kathode gegenüberliegende Glaskuppe mit einem kleinen Zückchen Aluminiumfolie beklebt, das mit der Anode leitend verbunden wird. Die nöthige Verdünnung hält sich auch bei diesen Röhren erst dann durch ein etwas längere Zeit, wenn man die Röhren einige Tage von Zeit zu Zeit zu Entladungen benutzt und gleich nachher wieder durch ein paar Pumpenschläge evacuirt.

The tubes recommended to you have proven to be very effective if you stick a small strip of aluminum foil which is connected to the anode on the glass dome opposite the cathode. With these tubes, too, the necessary dilution is only retained for a somewhat longer period of time if the tubes are used for discharges from time to time for a few days and immediately afterwards are evacuated again by a few strokes of the pump.

The tubes recommended to you have been working very well, provided a small piece of aluminium foil is stuck to the glass cap opposite the cathode and is connected with a lead to the anode. The necessary evacuation keeps in these tubes for a longer period but only if, for some days, one makes the tubes discharge from time to time and immediately afterwards evacuates them again, with a few strokes of the pump. (Translation Krebs) [11]

Roentgen already noted this in his "Vorläufige Mittheilung" (Preliminary Announcement) of December 1895, section 13:

Diese Erzeugung findet nicht nur in Glas statt, sondern, wie ich an einem mit 2 mm starkem Aluminiumblech abgeschlossenen Apparat beobachten konnte, auch in diesem Metall. Andere Substanzen sollen später untersucht werden.[12]

This production does not only take place in glass, but, as I was able to observe on an apparatus enclosed with 2 mm thick aluminum sheet, also in this metal.

This production does not take place in glass alone, but, as I have been able to observe in an apparatus closed by a plate of aluminum 2 millimeters thick, in this metal also. (Translation Krebs) [11]

Hertz had discovered that cathode rays pass through aluminum foil. He had proven this with a construction that was installed inside the tube. [10]

Lenard made a small hole in the tube and sealed it with aluminum foil with a thickness of 0.00265 mm (7.7 times as thick as conventional sheet foil) with the intention of examining the cathode rays outside the tube. [7] This allowed detection of fluorescence up to 8 cm under atmospheric pressure, but at a thickness of 0.027 mm the screen had to be held against the hole to still see fluorescence. [7]

But Roentgen saw a remote effect even with 2 mm thick aluminum. He also used different fluorescent material. Lenard used the organic penta-decylparatoly-ketone which is almost only sensitive to cathode rays, while Roentgen used the inorganic barium platinocyanide which is very sensitive to any form of light. [13] Roentgen had chosen this material consciously. In an interview with the English radiologist Mackenzie Davidson he says:

In Germany we use it to reveal the invisible rays of the spectrum, and I thought it a suitable substance to use to detect **any** (acc. KJS) invisible rays a tube might give off. [14]

He clearly states invisible rays and not cathode rays. Roentgen had something different in mind with his experimental setup. As follows from the arguments stated above, he was consciously on the lookout for the invisible rays he suspected.

Conclusion

Serendipity is discovering something that one is not looking for. Roentgen's discovery of X-rays is often cited as a classical example of this. We call for revision of this position. This article states that the choice of the experimental setup for the experiment of November 8, 1895 was not accidental, but purposeful. Roentgen was able to deduce some irregularities from publications by Lenard and Hertz. That probably made him decide to wrap Crookes's tube in cardboard. But also, he could read in their publications that an aluminum plate enhanced the fluorescence. He was looking for and found invisible radiation, albeit in a form that had not been discovered before.

We conclude that the discovery of X-rays was no serendipity. If one nevertheless wants to use the concept of serendipity in connection with X-rays, it is in the application to medicine. That, Roentgen could not have foreseen.

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